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Design and Implementation of a Multi-Protocol IoT Gateway Using PIC18 Controller

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ABSTRACT

The expansion of Internet of Things (IoT) networks has led to several communication protocols being utilized, causing interoperability problems between heterogeneous devices. Popular communication protocols like MQTT, BLE, and SPI have been used in IoT; however, no direct interoperability between the protocols was provided. In this paper, an architecture for developing an IoT gateway utilizing a resource-constrained PIC18F4520 microcontroller along with the ESP32 wireless module that serves as an interconnector of three pairs of protocols - MQTT and BLE, SPI and MQTT, and BLE and SPI, is proposed. With the resource constraints of the PIC18F4520 microcontroller consisting of 1.5 KB of RAM and 32 KB Flash, a firmware system with interrupt-based UART communication, small-size ring buffers, and Flash-based command storage is created. To protect the PIC18F4520 microcontroller running on a 5 V power source from potential damage, a TXS0102 bi-directional voltage level shifter was included to provide a reliable communication link between the 5 V PIC18F4520 microcontroller and 3.3 V ESP32 wireless module. All three protocol pairs were successfully implemented with a maximum of only 54% memory usage.

Keywords:- IoT gateway, protocol conversion, PIC18F4520, ESP32, MQTT, Bluetooth Low Energy, SPI, embedded systems, level shifting, resource-constrained design

INTRODUCTION

The IoT paradigm has revolutionized the way devices communicate, perform monitoring of surrounding environments and exchange information within distributed networks [5]. Contemporary IoT systems comprise an array of different communication protocols designed for various purposes ranging from power saving and reliable communication to wirelessness and real time operations [1].

For example, MQTT is a popular publish-subscribe protocol utilized for cloud-connected IoT applications [5], whereas BLE is a wireless short-range communication protocol operating with extremely low energy levels [1]. Likewise, SPI protocol is one of the most common interfaces used for communication between microcontrollers and peripheral components like memory modules, sensors, and display devices.

However, the problem arises due to the inability of these protocols to work together, thus making them inherently non-interoperable in heterogeneous IoT architectures. Numerous gateway implementations for bridging the gap between heterogeneous devices have been developed.

In fact, many commercially available IoT gateways are built on top of computer platforms based on Linux, e.g., Raspberry Pi or embedded industrial computers for performing protocol translation and network communications. Even though these systems feature sufficient computational capabilities and a wide array of communication protocols, they make the overall design more expensive and power-consuming compared to embedded systems.

In this paper, a multiple protocols IoT gateway with PIC18F4520 microcontroller as the main protocol

routing platform with an ESP32 wireless communication module is described. The PIC18F4520 microcontroller acts as a protocol routing machine whereas the ESP32 wireless communication module operates using AT-Command interface to provide Wi-Fi and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) support [2, 3].

Three protocol communication pairs have been implemented in the proposed gateway system: MQTT to BLE, SPI to MQTT, and BLE to SPI. To address the power supply voltage difference problem, a TXS0102 bidirectional level shifter circuit was used for electrical signal translation [4]. This paper illustrates how protocol interoperability is possible despite stringent constraints posed by the 8-bit microcontroller, which has 1.5 KB RAM and 32 KB Flash memory [2].

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Hardware Overview

The proposed gateway architecture combines the processing capabilities of the PIC18F4520 microcontroller with the wireless communication features of the ESP32 module. The PIC18F4520 serves as the central control unit responsible for protocol routing, state-machine execution, peripheral management, sensor acquisition, LCD updates, and communication control [2].

The ESP32 operates as a wireless coprocessor providing Wi-Fi and Bluetooth Low Energy functionality through UART-based AT commands [3]. The selection of the PIC18F4520 is motivated by its availability in a 40-pin Dual In-Line Package (DIP), making it suitable for breadboard prototyping, academic laboratory experimentation, and low-cost PCB implementation.

Although the device provides only 1,536 bytes of RAM and 32 KB of Flash memory, its 40 MHz operating capability,

integrated EUSART module, MSSP peripheral, EEPROM memory, and abundant GPIO resources make it suitable for protocol-routing applications [2]. Table I summarizes the key specifications of the PIC18F4520 and their impact on the proposed gateway design. The hardware platform additionally incorporates a DHT22 temperature and humidity sensor, a 16×2 LCD module with I²C backpack, three protocol-selection toggle switches, four status-

indication LEDs, and a TXS0102 voltage-level translator [4]. The DHT22 provides environmental data for MQTT publication demonstrations, while the LCD presents real-time gateway status and active protocol information. Three user-operated switches allow selection of the desired protocol pair, ensuring that only one communication route remains active at any given time to minimize memory utilization and simplify firmware management.

Table 1:-PIC18F4520 Key Specifications and Project Impact

Specification	Value	Impact on Project
Architecture	8-bit RISC PIC18	Sufficient for protocol routing logic
CPU Speed	40 MHz	Fast enough for UART + SPI + routing
Flash Memory	32 KB	Tight firmware must be lean
RAM	1,536 bytes	Critical constraint drives all design decisions
EEPROM	256 bytes	Store WiFi SSID, MQTT broker address
SPI / I ² C	1x MSSP	SPI and I ² C cannot be active simultaneously
UART	1x EUSART	Used for ESP32 AT commands
Operating Voltage	4.2 V - 5.5 V	Mismatch with ESP32 (3.3 V) requires level shifter

Voltage-Level Translation

Whereas the PIC18F4520 works with a voltage of 5V, the ESP32 works with voltage levels of 3.3V [2, 3]. Directly connecting the transmit pin of the PIC18F4520 to that of the ESP32 would cause potential damage to the ESP32 due to over-voltage problems.

Therefore, a TXS0102 level translator is used to ensure the proper transmission of the signals [4]. The TXS0102 bidirectional level translator converts signals in two directions without requiring any direction control circuitry [4]. Its speed, small size, and cost-effectiveness make it ideal for transmitting high-speed digital signals in this application.

Dual Power Rail

This kind of power supply satisfies the structural requirements of both controllers. The power that comes from the stable 5V power supply is provided directly to the PIC18F4520, the LCD display, the status LEDs, and the toggle buttons. The ESP32 uses an AMS1117-3.3 step-down DC-DC linear regulator where the output voltage is 3.3V while the input voltage is drawn from the 5V rail.

To improve power stability, 100 nF ceramic decoupling capacitors are placed close to the VCC and GND pins of each IC to filter high-frequency noise. Additionally, 10 μF bulk electrolytic capacitors are implemented across the

power rails to reduce transient voltage drops during high-current wireless transmissions.

FIRMWARE AND PROTOCOL DESIGN

Memory Budget Analysis

With RAM limited to just 1,536 bytes, optimal static memory usage is vital [2]. The memory is allocated appropriately to communication buffers, protocol data, LCD data, and firmware variables as demonstrated in Table II below.

This design utilizes about 836 bytes of memory, which translates to a 54% utilization rate of the total available RAM. The UART buffer is restricted to 64 bytes each, and protocol payload memory consumption is kept minimal.

The constant AT commands are stored entirely in the Flash memory [3], dynamic memory allocation (malloc) is strictly avoided, and small uint8_t data types are employed where appropriate to maximize data efficiency.

Table 2:-RAM Budget: PIC18F4520 (1,536 Bytes Total)

Usage	Bytes	Notes
UART TX ring buffer	64	Single AT command string
UART RX ring buffer	64	One response at a time
SPI data buffer	32	DHT22 single packet
Active protocol pair data buffer	64	Current conversion payload
AT command string (RAM)	64	Temporary buffer built from Flash template
LCD display buffer	32	Two 16-character lines
Software stack	256	Function calls + Interrupt Service Routines (ISRs)
Local variables + flags	100	State machine execution + loop counters
EUSART RX ISR buffer	32	Interrupt-driven hardware capture
Reserved / overhead	128	Safety margin for runtime stability
TOTAL USED	836	54% Utilization

Firmware State Machine

The firmware architecture uses a structured finite state machine (FSM) design. Following sequential initialization of the internal peripherals and wireless communication via the ESP32 module, the controller continuously monitors the physical hardware protocol-selection switches and dynamically sets the proper routing mode. There can be only one active protocol pair at any one given time; thus, this execution restriction helps

manage hardware resources and saves significantly on volatile memory usage.

The UART receive buffer is managed strictly through hardware interrupts, and internal watchdog timers are used to determine if any communication stalls or errors occur. In such cases, the LCD screen displays a diagnostic error message, a dedicated fault LED illuminates, and an automated software recovery sequence is attempted.

Protocol Pair Data Flows***MQTT to BLE Communication:***

During MQTT-BLE communication mode, the wireless message is received at the ESP32 module after publication via the cloud-based HiveMQ broker [5]. Next, the payload is delivered to the PIC18F4520 microcontroller over the hardware UART interface [2, 3].

Processing the payload according to routing logic, the main PIC18F4520 board directs the ESP32 coprocessor to broadcast the payload over the air via BLE [3]. Successful data delivery is indicated visually with the help of a blue status LED and an LCD status message.

SPI to MQTT Communication:

During SPI-MQTT communication, environmental information from the hardware sensors is collected in a form of structured messages periodically. The collected payload is sent via UART by the PIC18F4520 to the ESP32 microcontroller [2]. Subsequently, the ESP32 transmits the data packets via Wi-Fi to the remote cloud MQTT broker [5]. The green status LED and LCD screen update indicate that the translation process was successful.

BLE to SPI Communication:

In BLE-SPI communication mode, the control commands sent by an external BLE client are captured and transmitted via the ESP32 to the PIC18F4520 microcontroller [2,3]. The microcontroller processes and executes the command by performing master SPI transactions to local peripheral devices. Transaction completion is reported locally with the help of a yellow status LED and an LCD screen message.

DESIGN ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION**Constraint-Driven Design Decisions**

The physical and logical design of the system is heavily constrained by the strict lack of RAM and embedded peripherals in the 8-bit PIC18F4520 microcontroller. The integration of a graphic TFT display was discarded early in development due to its high video memory footprint compared to the total available 1.5 KB RAM. Instead, a lightweight, standard character-based 16×2 LCD is employed to show the state of the process.

To minimize concurrent memory usage, only one protocol pair runs simultaneously at a time. Moreover, implementing an I²C interface in software (bit-banging mode) for the LCD display frees up the single hardware MSSP peripheral exclusively for high-speed SPI communication [2].

Trade-offs vs. Alternative Architectures

Several hardware voltage-level shifting solutions were evaluated, including passive resistor dividers, logic-gate buffers, and discrete MOSFET-based circuits. Table III provides an overview of these technical options. The TXS0102 IC was selected because it provides automatic, high-speed bidirectional translation with minimal external component circuitry [4].

Compared with high-end 16-bit PIC24 and 32-bit PIC32 devices, the 8-bit PIC18F4520 offers lower memory capacity but significantly reduced unit cost, lower power, and minimal circuit complexity.

Despite its limitations, it adequately supports the core protocol routing, peripheral control, and communication management, making it highly suitable for educational laboratories and low-cost embedded applications.

Table 2:-Alternative Level-Shifting Solutions

Method	How It Works	Cost (INR)	Verdict
TXS0102 (Selected)	Auto bidirectional level shift	15 - 25	Best Choice: Bidirectional, high speed, reliable.
Voltage Divider (2R)	10 kΩ + 20 kΩ resistors on TX only	2	Unidirectional only; safe for TX line, risks RX mismatch.
74HC4050 Buffer	5 V to 3.3 V level shifting, one direction	10	Unidirectional only; requires multiple channels/ ICs.
BSS138 MOSFET	Discrete open-drain level shift	5	DIY circuit; slower data rates, higher component count.
Direct Connection	No shifter hardware used	0	DANGEROUS: Will cause over-voltage damage to ESP32.

Scalability and Limitations

The primary design reason for implementing just one active protocol combination is the restriction caused by the limited RAM along with a single built-in hardware UART communication port on the PIC18F4520 [2]. Simultaneous operation of all protocol routes would need increased dynamic memory, higher processing clock speeds, and more complex multi-threaded task handling.

Further industrial scalability developments may use advanced microcontrollers that can provide higher hardware performance due to having larger integrated static RAM and multiple independent hardware UART modules. Also, alternative industrial communication protocols, including CAN, Zigbee, LoRa, or Modbus, could be natively added into the gateway routing machine.

CONCLUSION

The proposed design demonstrates a highly resource-constrained IoT Gateway which utilizes a PIC18F4520 and an ESP32 wireless module. The developed hardware prototype successfully showcased interoperable, stable

communication across three heterogeneous protocols (MQTT, BLE, and SPI) while working under the tight constraints of having 1.5 KB RAM and 32 KB Flash storage. Reliable intercommunication of the 5V and 3.3V components was achieved through the use of the TXS0102 voltage level shifter, keeping total system RAM usage optimized at around 54%.

Future upgrades will focus on increasing the volatile and non-volatile capacities of the main microcontroller, enabling true parallel protocol handling, the operational incorporation of an embedded Real-Time Operating System (RTOS), transition to the lightweight MQTT-SN protocol, and final production design of an SMD-based professional PCB layout.

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